

On the functions of hedging in research articles (RAs): A study on RA discussions

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The current study aimed at finding probable differences between native-Persian-speaking ($n = 72$) and native-English-speaking ($n = 72$) academic writers' use of hedging devices in the 'discussion' sections of research articles (RAs). 144 RA discussions from Persian-text Iranian academic journals published by Iranian state universities and English-text foreign academic journals published by several famous international academic publishers were randomly selected. The publication dates of the RAs ranged from 2017 to 2022. Using a counter-balanced design, two human coders identified and coded the functions of hedging devices in the corpus according to the theoretical framework proposed by Hyland (1998). Results indicated that Iranian authors of Persian-text RAs systematically use much fewer hedging devices in their discussions than their foreign counterparts. It is argued that this pattern might be due to Iranian RA authors' (a) personality traits, (b) incompetence in academic writing, or (c) cultural mindset. The paper concludes that professional workshops in which native-Persian-speaking authors are taught to be aware of the importance of hedging devices in academic writing might be necessary and that journal editors should also have an eye on the use of hedging in the process of screening the manuscripts they receive for possible publication in the journals they edit.

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1. Introduction

Writing in English as the mainstream and global language for academic communication has been extensively studied and has received considerable

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attention from linguists and applied linguists. Many of the papers and books written in English on the topic of academic writing have evaluated it from a 'genre' perspective (cf. Bhatia & Salmani Nodoushan, 2015; Hopkins & Dudley-Evans, 1988; Rasmeenin, 2006; Salmani Nodoushan, 2012; Swales, 1971, 1981, 1990, 2004; Yang & Allison, 2003). It is also well-accepted that academic writing in English has clear rules and principles (cf. Alavi & Salmani Nodoushan, 2004; Birjandi et al., 2004) that have been expounded in course books written by outstanding academics around the world (e.g., Swales & Feak, 1994, 2000). Nevertheless, there are no noticeable published works that have studied academic writing in Persian. Many Persian-text academic journals are published in Iran, and the authors who publish their research papers in such journals write them in Persian because the default language of text for these journals is Persian. The majority of authors contributing to these journals have been trained (a) in Iran, (b) in Persian, and (c) by teachers and professors who are not that familiar with academic English as the international language of science. Moreover, there are not any academic writing courses in Persian, and the few existing composition classes are mainly focused on the 'mechanics of writing'. In fact, the way writing is taught in Persian is anything but professional (cf. Khakbaz & Salmani Nodoushan, 2012). It is therefore hypothesized that such authors might not know the rules and principles of academic writing.

Because hedging is an important topic in academic writing in general, and writing for specific purposes in specific (cf. Donadio, 2019; Francomacaro, 2019; Ortu, 2019), it is vital that we study academic writing in Persian to see whether authors from non-linguistic disciplines know and use the rules and principles of academic writing in their publications. The current study, therefore, focused on the functions of hedging in the 'discussion' subgenre of research articles (RAs) written in Persian and published in Persian-text academic journals in Iran. The study compared such RAs with those written by native-English-speaking academic writers whose works are disseminated in famous English-text journals published by famous international academic publishers.

2. Background

Hedging, as a linguistic category and mainly a pragmatic one, plays an important part in the effectiveness of academic writing. It is one of the affordances of language that writers use 'creatively' (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2018a) to accomplish certain effects on their readers. Hedges can indicate hesitation, uncertainty, indirectness, reservation, politeness, and/or avoidance of commitment regarding what is being claimed, said, or written (Nwogu, 1997; Hyland, 1998; Salager-Meyer, 1994; Varttala, 1999). According to Varttala (2001), hedging typically serves such functions as (a) modulating

truth value, (b) commenting on the accuracy of a given conceptualization, and/or (c) influencing the truthfulness and force of propositions.

Nevertheless, there is no single agreement on the correct and precise definition of hedging. One definition has been given by Lakoff (1973, p. 458), who saw hedges as a group of words “whose meaning implicitly involves fuzziness—words whose job is to make things fuzzier” By way of contrast, Hyland (1998, p. 1) defined hedging as the “lack of complete commitment to the truth value of an accompanying proposition.” He also suggested that hedges might very often be “polypragmatic” (Hyland, 1996b, p. 437) because they can be used for a variety of pragmatic functions depending on the communication situation; they are pragmatic in nature.

Along the same lines, Crismore and Vande Kopple (1988) suggested that hedging may be a ‘language game’ (cf. Capone and Salmani Nodoushan, 2014; Salmani Nodoushan, 2016b), that is used to signal caution or tentativeness when people seek to express some information. Brown and Levinson (1978, 1987) have suggested that hedging serves (linguistic) politeness in interpersonal communication (see also Allami & Salmani Nodoushan, 2011; Watts et al., 1992); it is a form of politeness used to protect positive face, a topic that has emerged from Grice’s conversational maxims (Salmani Nodoushan, 2022). Likewise, Salager-Meyer et al. (1996) saw hedges as rhetorical, semantic and pragmatic devices in scientific genres used to relate authors to their readership in the discourse context. They suggested five functions for hedging: (1) creating purposive mistiness and vagueness as a threat-minimizing strategy; (2) reducing claims about the strength, certainty, or truth of propositions; (3) expressing tentativeness and flexibility; (4) projecting modesty for achievements and politeness with the peer community; and (5) avoiding personal involvement and discharging direct responsibility. These functions are essentially a modification of Salager-Meyer’s (1994) five categories of hedges: (1) shields, (2) approximators, (3) personal expressions, (4) emotionally charged intensifiers, and (5) compound hedges—see also Ädel (2006) and Prince et al. (1982).

In a similar vein, Mauranen (1997, p. 115) argued that hedging allows for “uncertainties, indirectness, and non-finality” in academic writing. It allows RA authors to present their scientific claims cautiously, tentatively, diplomatically, and modestly; this is vital because their target community and readership is academic and may have certain expectations (Hyland, 1998; Salager-Meyer, 1997). Similarly, Dubois (1997) claimed that hedging bridges hypotheses and facts and, at the same time, protects authors against harsh criticism by creating ‘a continuum between all and no’.

In academic writing, hedging is often realized as a set of metadiscursive lexicogrammatical structures or coherence strategies that allow authors to

avoid responsibility (Hinkel, 1997). It is a cautious way that gives authors the chance to be accepted in interpersonal relationships (Nikula, 1997). Academic writers use hedging as a type of interpersonal metadiscourse to (a) signal hesitation or caution, (b) share information in a graceful and decent way, and (c) lessen the effects of face-threatening acts (see also Salmani Nodoushan, 2016a, 2021a). According to Paltridge and Starfield (2007, p. 52), hedging is a significant element of students' theses because "This is where the linguistic resources known as 'hedgers' become extremely important to the second-language thesis writer as they learn how to adjust the strength of their claims in relation to their audience and communicative purpose."

All of the considerations described above show that hedging can be a tool that gives authors the power to convince their readers in scientific contexts; "hedging is the mark of a professional scientist, one who acknowledges the care with which he or she does science and writes on science" (Crismore & Farnsworth, 1990, p. 135). It is because of this that academic writing and hedging have been studied by many people; specifically, types and functions of hedging have been probed extensively. Beginning in the mid-1980s, research on academic performance and hedging has ever since (a) been mainly pointed at written discourse and (b) has addressed academically- and scientifically-oriented language use (Salager-Meyer, 1994; Hyland, 2000). Many studies have approached academic writing in general, and hedging in specific, from many different perspectives. Examples include biomedical slide meetings (Dubois, 1987), economic debates (Dudley-Evans, 1993; Bloor & Bloor, 1993), scientific research articles (Myers, 1989; Hyland, 1996a; 1998), medicine (Salager-Meyer, 1994; Nwogu, 1997; Varttala, 1999), and so forth.

Due to its importance, Hyland (1998) developed a descriptive model (i.e., the Polypragmatic Model of Hedging Functions) that shows the orientations and functions of hedging in academic communication—and specifically in writing. As a theoretical model, the Polypragmatic Model of Hedging Functions shows the multi-functional nature of hedging in academic discourse. According to this model, hedges can cover a rich class of textual elements that fulfil a multitude of communicative functions. Hedging plays some role in, for instance, English for Specific Purposes (cf. Johns & Salmani Nodoushan, 2015), theses and dissertations (cf. Khakbaz & Salmani Nodoushan, 2011, 2012), book reviews (cf. Montazeran & Salmani Nodoushan, 2012), conversations (cf. Kazemi & Salmani Nodoushan, 2017, 2018; Lee, 2021; Wan, 2023), language assessment (cf. Brown & Salmani Nodoushan, 2015; Karami & Salmani Nodoushan, 2011, 2014; Salmani Nodoushan, 2020b), genre analysis (cf. Bhatia & Salmani Nodoushan, 2015), and so forth. According to Hyland (1998, p. 160), hedging devices can "weaken force of statements, contain modal expressions, express deference, signal uncertainty, and so on." A schematic representation of Hyland's Polypragmatic Model of Hedging Functions is depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1.

Hyland's Polypragmatic Model of Hedging Functions

As this model shows, Hyland (1998) has divided hedges (specifically in the 'discussion' subgenre) into two basic classes: (1) content-oriented hedges, and (2) reader-oriented hedges. According to Hyland (1996a), content-oriented hedges "mitigate the relationship between propositional content and a representation of reality; they hedge the correspondence between what the writer says about the world and what the world is thought to be like" (Hyland, 1996a, p. 439)—see also Hyland (1998). In this connection, hedging devices (i.e., main verbs, modal auxiliaries, adverbs, adjectives, and/or nouns) are classified as 'attribute' hedges if they try to mitigate the accuracy of the term that describes the phenomenon being reported in the text. However, if hedging devices try to mitigate the writer's assessment of the precision of (the truth) of a claim, they are grouped as reliability hedges. Finally, if they mitigate the writer's direct acceptance of responsibility for the truth of the proposition being described, the hedges are classified as writer-oriented hedging devices.

By way of contrast, reader-oriented hedges bear on the relationship between authors and their readership; reader-oriented hedges "confirm the attention writers give to the interactional effects of their statements" and "solicit collusion by addressing the reader as an intelligent colleague capable of participating in the discourse with an open mind" (Hyland, 1996a, p. 446). According to Hyland (1998), authors often use adjectives, adverbs, modal auxiliaries, nouns, certain content verbs, and so forth as hedging devices in

their academic writing. If such devices (a) signal that the writer willingly ‘accepts responsibility’ or (b) ‘show that the writer invites the readership to get involved’ in the discourse, the hedging devices are classified as reader-oriented. Table 1 summarizes hedging devices described in Hyland’s (1998, p. 186) model.

Table 1

Summary of Hedging Functions and Devices (Hyland, 1998, p. 186)

Accuracy-Oriented	Writer-oriented	Reader-oriented
Attribution	Epistemic verbs:	Epistemic verbs:
Precision adverbs	• judgmental	• judgmental
Content disjuncts	• evidential	• deductive
Style disjuncts	Impersonal expressions:	Personal attribution
Downtoners	• passive voice	Personal reference to:
Reliability	• abstract rhetors	• methods
Epistemic verbs	• empty subjects	• models
Modal verbs	Attribution to literature	Hypotheticals
Epistemic adjectives	Reference to:	Involve reader:
Epistemic nouns	• methods	• direct questions
Content disjuncts	• models	• offer alternatives

It should be noted that in any written text, the author is the sender of message and the reader is the receiver of it, so there is an addressor-addressee relationship. However, this is not the only kind of relationship; the writer has also a normative-scientific duty that obliges him/her “to defer to the views of colleagues, adhere to limits on self-assurance and engage in debate with peers” (Hyland, 1996a, p. 446). As a result, the difference between content-oriented and reader-oriented hedges is basically the fact that content-oriented hedging is related to ‘accuracy’, but reader-oriented hedges bear on principles and ethics that control and manage interpersonal relationships between authors and their audience (i.e., show that authors yield respectfully to their readership in judgment or opinion); these hedges govern protocols that are part of the codes of ethical and scientific conduct in any professional and academic community of practice.

Nevertheless, much—if not all—of the studies that have addressed hedging in academic writing have been conducted in and on the English language. To our knowledge, however, no study has researched hedging in academic texts written in Persian, nor has any study compared hedging in Persian-text RA discussions to those in English-text RAs. The current study, therefore, sought to see if native-Persian-speaking Iranian and native-English-speaking foreign authors’ RA discussions differ in their use of hedging functions.

3. Method

The current study drew on Hyland's (1998) Polypragmatic Model of Hedging Functions to investigate the probable differences that might be found in Persian- versus English-text RA discussions. It was hypothesized that Iranian authors of RA discussions would differ from their foreign counterparts in their writing of RA discussions in terms of their use of content-oriented (i.e., both accuracy-oriented and writer-oriented) and reader-oriented hedges.

3.1. The corpus

The corpus for this study included 144 RA discussions randomly chosen from six different disciplines (i.e., three hard-science and three soft-science disciplines). Table 2 displays the structure of the corpus that was used for purposes of the current study.

Table 2

The Structure of the Corpus of the Current Study

Author Group	Discipline	No. of discussions	Tokens
Iranian	Medicine	12	11,696
	Chemistry	12	12,972
	Civil Engineering	12	10,836
	Sociology	12	12,448
	Psychology	12	13,104
	Anthropology	12	12,492
Foreign	Medicine	12	12,976
	Chemistry	12	13,916
	Civil Engineering	12	12,496
	Sociology	12	13,572
	Psychology	12	12,776
	Anthropology	12	14,508

The disciplines that belonged in hard sciences in the current study include (a) medicine, (b) chemistry, and (c) civil Engineering; those belonging in the category of soft sciences include (a) sociology, (b) psychology, and (c) anthropology. Soft and hard sciences were defined in terms of (a) the precision of their concepts and (b) their methods of quantification. There may be some disagreement about psychology being classified as a soft science, but it was grouped in that class based on the above criteria. All of the RAs in the corpus were reports of quantitative research studies.

3.2. Participants

The participants in this study are in fact the authors of the RAs whose written works were randomly selected as the corpus for this study. Because each RA has a corresponding author, it was decided that each paper—even if it was a multi-author paper—should be seen as the written production of its corresponding author (i.e., this decision is a ‘delimitation’ of the current study). Since (a) the publication-date range included between 2017 and 2022 (i.e., six years), (b) there were six disciplines (i.e., medicine, chemistry, civil engineering, sociology, psychology, and anthropology), (c) there were two author groups (i.e., Iranian versus foreign), and (d) from each year two ‘quantitative’ papers were randomly selected, the total participant size added up to 144 (i.e., $N = 144$).

3.3. Procedure

After the corpus was randomly selected, two professional applied linguists coded the corpus using Hyland’s (1998) Polypragmatic Model of Hedging Functions as the analytical framework. Each of these applied linguists had a minimum of 15 years of experience in teaching academic writing to graduate EFL students. Before asking them to look for hedges in the corpus, we gave each RA discussion a unique identification number so that confusion would not find any chance to happen when the obtained data were input to *IBM SPSS* for analysis. RA discussions from the hard-science corpus were consecutively coded as #H1, #H2, #H3, etc., and those from the soft-science corpus received #S1, #S2, #S3, etc.

The human coders were asked to use a counter-balanced coding design; the first applied linguist coded all of the soft-science RA discussions first; after a two-week interval, she coded the hard-science RA discussions. This procedure was reversed for the second applied linguist; he first coded the hard-science RA discussions, and after a two-week interval, he coded the soft-science RA discussions. In this way, we made sure that no carry-over or practice effect would cause imprecision in our data.

When the two applied linguists turned in their codings, the data were fed to *IBM SPSS* (version 24.0). Inter-coder reliability analysis was performed using Spearman-Brown’s *rho*, and it was estimated at $\rho = 0.843$. For inferential analyses, Mann-Whitney *U* tests were used.

4. Results

In this section, overall comparisons as well as comparisons within hard and soft sciences are reported. It should be noted that in all of the following

analyses, the group with a larger median is the group that has used the relevant hedging function more frequently than the other group.

4.1. Overall comparisons

To compare Iranian and foreign authors' overall performance in connection to accuracy-oriented hedging devices, a Mann-Whitney U test was performed. The results showed a significant difference in the use of hedging devices by the Iranian authors ($Md = 20$, $n = 72$) and their foreign counterparts ($Md = 26.5$, $n = 72$), $U = 4093$, $z = 6.009$, $p = .000$, $r = .501$. To calculate the effect size (i.e., the r value), we divided the z value by the square root of N (i.e., $N = 144$). Based on Cohen's (1988) criteria (i.e., .1 = small effect, .3 = medium effect, .5 = large effect), the observed difference was large. The median of the foreign author group showed that they had used accuracy-oriented hedging devices more frequently than those in the Iranian group. Another Mann-Whitney U test was performed to compare the two groups' use of writer-oriented hedging devices. The results showed a significant difference in the use of hedging devices by Iranian authors ($Md = 21.5$, $n = 72$) and foreign authors ($Md = 52$, $n = 72$), $U = 4989$, $z = 9.57$, $p = .000$, $r = .797$. Cohen's criteria indicated that the observed difference was large. The median of the foreign group showed that authors in this group had used writer-oriented hedging devices much more frequently than those in the Iranian group. The third Mann-Whitney U test was performed to compare the two groups' use of reader-oriented hedging devices. The results showed a significant difference in the use of hedging devices by Iranian ($Md = 41$, $n = 72$) and foreign authors ($Md = 84$, $n = 72$), $U = 5184$, $z = 10.381$, $p = .000$, $r = .865$. Based on Cohen's criteria, the observed difference was large. The median of the foreign group showed that authors in this group had used much more reader-oriented hedging devices than those in the Iranian group.

4.2. Comparisons in hard sciences

As stated above, the papers selected for analysis in this study belonged in six disciplines—three disciplines from hard sciences (i.e., medicine, chemistry, and civil Engineering) and three disciplines from soft sciences (i.e., sociology, psychology, and anthropology). Using the 'select cases' option from *IBS SPSS*, we selected all of the cases that belonged to hard sciences and then compared our Iranian and foreign author groups. To see if the two groups differed in their use of accuracy-oriented hedging devices, we used a Mann-Whitney U test. The results showed a significant difference in the use of accuracy-oriented hedging devices by Iranian hard-science authors ($Md = 18$, $n = 36$) and their foreign counterparts ($Md = 22$, $n = 36$), $U = 1248$, $z = 6.813$, $p = .000$, $r = .802$. To calculate the effect size, we divided the z value by the square root of N (i.e., $N = 72$). Based on Cohen's criteria, the observed difference was large. The median of the foreign group showed that authors in this group had used relatively more

accuracy-oriented hedging devices than those in the Iranian group. Another Mann-Whitney U test was performed to compare the two groups' use of writer-oriented hedging devices. The results showed a significant difference in the use of hedging devices by Iranian authors ($Md = 10.5, n = 36$) and foreign authors ($Md = 32, n = 36$), $U = 1296, z = 7.313, p = .000, r = .861$. Cohen's criteria indicated that the observed difference was large. The median of the foreign group showed that authors in this group had used many more writer-oriented hedging devices than those in the Iranian group. Another Mann-Whitney U test was performed to compare the two groups' use of reader-oriented hedging devices. Here again, the results showed a significant difference in the use of hedging devices by Iranian authors ($Md = 41, n = 36$) and foreign authors ($Md = 84, n = 36$), $U = 1298, z = 7.317, p = .000, r = .862$. Cohen's criteria indicated that the observed difference was large. The median of the foreign group showed that authors in this group had used reader-oriented hedging devices much more frequently than their Iranian counterparts.

4.3. Comparisons in soft sciences

To compare Iranian and foreign soft-science academic authors, we used the 'select cases' option of *IBS SPSS* to choose all of the cases that belonged to soft sciences and then compared the Iranian and the foreign author groups using another set of Mann-Whitney U tests. To see if the two groups differed in their use of accuracy-oriented hedging devices, we used a Mann-Whitney U test of which the results showed a significant difference between the Iranian soft-science authors ($Md = 27, n = 36$) and their foreign counterparts ($Md = 49, n = 36$), $U = 1239, z = 6.679, p = .000, r = .787$. To calculate the effect size, we divided the z value by the square root of N (i.e., $N = 72$). Based on Cohen's criteria, the effect size was large. The median of the foreign group showed that authors in this group had used relatively more accuracy-oriented hedging devices than those in the Iranian group. Another Mann-Whitney U test was performed to compare the two groups' use of writer-oriented hedging devices. The results showed a significant difference between the Iranian authors ($Md = 28, n = 36$) and foreign authors ($Md = 69, n = 36$), $U = 1296, z = 7.371, p = .000, r = .868$. Cohen's criteria indicated that the observed difference was large. The median of the foreign group showed that soft-science authors in this group had used many more writer-oriented hedging devices than those in the Iranian soft-science author group. The last Mann-Whitney U test compared the two groups' use of reader-oriented hedging devices. Here again, the results showed a significant difference in the use of hedging devices by Iranian authors ($Md = 41, n = 36$) and foreign authors ($Md = 84, n = 36$), $U = 1299, z = 7.321, p = .000, r = .863$. Cohen's criteria indicated that the observed difference was large. The median of the foreign group showed that authors in this group had used

reader-oriented hedging devices much more frequently than their Iranian counterparts.

5. Discussion

This study set out to see if native-Persian-speaking Iranian writers of Persian RAs differ from native-English-speaking foreign writers of English RAs in their use of accuracy-, writer-, and reader-oriented hedging devices. Figure 2 visualizes median comparisons between the two author groups, and Table 3 summarizes the findings.

Figure 2.

Median Comparisons Between Iranian and Foreign Author Groups

Table 3
Summary of the Mann-Whitney U test Results

		<i>U</i>	<i>z</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>r</i>	Effect Size
Overall	Accuracy-Oriented	4093	6.009	.000	.501	Large
	Writer-Oriented	4989	9.570	.000	.797	Large
	Reader-Oriented	5184	10.381	.000	.865	Large
Hard Sciences	Accuracy-Oriented	1248	6.813	.000	.802	Large
	Writer-Oriented	1296	7.313	.000	.861	Large
	Reader-Oriented	1298	7.317	.000	.862	Large
Soft Sciences	Accuracy-Oriented	1239	6.679	.000	.787	Large
	Writer-Oriented	1296	7.371	.000	.868	Large
	Reader-Oriented	1299	7.321	.000	.863	Large

The results reported in section 4 have shown that, overall, Iranian academic authors of Persian-text RAs published in Persian-text academic journals systematically use fewer hedging devices. This might indicate (a) that they probably do not know much about the importance of such devices as well as their functions in academic writing or (b) that academic Persian differs in its sensitivity to precision and clarity from academic English. This stands in stark contrast to Crismore and Farnsworth's (1990) claim that "hedging is the mark of a professional scientist, one who acknowledges the care with which he or she does science and writes on science" (p. 135).

As for accuracy-oriented hedging device, the situation is much worse in soft sciences than in hard sciences. This means that in hard sciences, due to their very nature, the use of accuracy-oriented hedging devices is not that necessary; academic authors in soft sciences, however, are expected to be well aware of the imprecision of their disciplines. The fact that foreign soft-science authors [median = 49] have used almost twice as many accuracy-oriented hedging devices in their RA discussions as their Iranian counterparts [median = 27] shows that the Iranian group probably needs to receive professional training on the principles and subtleties of academic discourse. This lends support to other studies (e.g., Allahverdi et al., 2023; Hernandez, 2020, 2021, 2022, 2023; Salmani Nodoushan, 2023b) that claim that junior authors need to be instructed on how they should write appropriate RAs. Another explanation might be that they know these conventions but are culturally reluctant to use them that frequently; it is commonly agreed among more proficient academics in Iran that some less proficient soft-science academics who have received their professional education in Iran—and whose teachers had not been educated in Anglo-American universities—often tend to project a bloated scientific self-image and see their disciplines as quite precise, so they normally talk about themes and issues in their fields with an overwhelmingly-and-whimsically high level of self-confidence. In other words, the reason why

Iranian soft-science authors are so reluctant to use accuracy-oriented hedging might possibly be that they are self-centered and/or presumptuous; this is unfortunately a sub-conscious cultural trait that needs to be corrected through self-monitoring, self-awareness and self-regulation. We would like to refer to this erratic form of academic conduct as 'pixyish whimsical academic arrogance' which is far from true professionalism (cf. Pashapour & Salmani Nodoushan, 2016). Needless to say, this is a false cultural mindset that needs to be corrected through academic training and critical pedagogy (cf. Daftarifard & Salmani Nodoushan, 2011). It points to the importance of attention to cultural factors in school and university curricula (cf. Dabbagh et al., 2023).

Likewise, Iranian and foreign authors showed a huge difference in connection to writer-oriented hedging devices too. While foreign authors' RA discussions had used many more evidential epistemic verbs and passive constructions, Iranian authors' RA discussions included many more judgmental epistemic verbs and active voice. This might have a cultural and/or a linguistic explanation. Culturally, Iranian academic writers not/less familiar with western conventions of academic writing seem to accept more personal responsibility in connection to the claims they make; this might have to do with their personality traits (cf. Al Shalabi & Salmani Nodoushan, 2009). Linguistically, Persian and English do not completely copy each other's norms and conventions. The use of passive voice as well as impersonal language, which might allow the agent to remain outside of focus or completely hidden, is an accepted norm in academic writing in English (especially in hard sciences), but this is not necessarily the case in Persian. Accepting greater personal responsibility on the part of Iranian authors of RAs, in addition to their incompetence in academic writing, might also show that they probably bring their personal traits (cf. Al Shalabi & Salmani Nodoushan, 2009) into their academic writing tasks, a situation that is also seen in their reading performance (cf. Nemati et al., 2010). A similar study might want to use authors' personality traits (e.g., pompousness, presumptuousness, self-centeredness, etc.) as independent/intervening variables to compare groups of authors showing these traits with other groups and see if there is a statistically significant difference in their use of writer-oriented hedging devices.

Likewise, Persian academic writers tend to use much less reader-oriented hedging devices in their RA discussions than their foreign counterparts. This is a shame because respecting one's interlocutors is a fundamental issue in interpersonal communication (cf. Allan & Salmani Nodoushan, 2015), and writing is no exception. RA authors need to see their readership as intelligent people who can be engaged in professional interaction, but not as empty containers that needs to be filled with information. Where an academic author opts for the latter, he or she is essentially disregarding his/her interlocutor. Reader-oriented hedging devices are tools for showing 'politeness', and

politeness within a community of practice is of utmost importance; as Hyland (1998, p. 446) argued, reader-oriented hedging devices “confirm the attention writers give to the interactional effects of their statements” and “solicit collusion by addressing the reader as an intelligent colleague capable of participating in the discourse with an open mind.” In spite of this, Iranian authors in the current study have used much fewer reader-oriented hedging devices in comparison to their foreign counterparts. This might also be due to a cultural mindset that argues that politeness is not that necessary when people belong to a closely-friendly cohort; this lends support to the claim made by Salmani Nodoushan (2016a) that impoliteness can sometimes have the social ‘affordance’, à la Salmani Nodoushan (2021c), of showing intimacy. Nevertheless, academic writing is a formal, and perhaps frozen, genre governed by certain agreed-upon principles, and Iranian academic authors need to be trained to leave their local cultural mindset behind the door before they start to write a RA. They need to learn the fact that writing a RA needs a procedural process of acting based on certain conventions and protocols.

6. Conclusion

Based on the results reported in section 4 and the discussion presented in section 5, it might be concluded that there is a substantial difference between Persian and English in terms of the use of hedging devices in academic writing. Nevertheless, It is important to note that the current study (a) did not include a large sample in its corpus, and that (b) only a few disciplines from hard and soft sciences were studied in a limited time range. This means that the findings reported above are not based on a very large corpus to afford any generalization; the results of the study have shown some areas of concern, though. Perhaps a richer corpus that consists of a large number of RAs from a wide range of academic disciplines over a much wider range of time might produce similar or different findings. Moreover, the findings of this study might be compared to similar studies (if any) conducted in other languages to see if the patterns found in this study are local or universal. The main advantage of this study, however, is that it is the first study, to our knowledge, to have investigated the functions of hedging in Persian-text RA discussions.

The findings of the current study clearly indicate that Iranian RA authors lag behind the accepted norms of academic writing practiced in English—i.e., the international language of science. Our findings, therefore, have implications for language teaching and professional training. It seems that Iranian academic authors, specifically those in soft sciences, are not well aware of the existence and/or importance of hedging devices. They might need to be trained, perhaps in ‘professional development workshops’ (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2023a), to use these types of hedging in their writings. The main ‘washback’ (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2021c) of the current study on teaching is that hard-science

authors of RAs need to be made aware of the importance of authorial voice (cf. Boginskaya, 2022) in professional writings; where there is certainty and precision in the findings of a study conducted in hard precise sciences, there is no reason to allow self-defacement (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2021a) to affect or obliterate their importance, and hard-science authors of RAs need to have a stronger authorial voice to establish their own authoritativeness through what Salmani Nodoushan (2023b) has called 'ethos in academic writing'. Readership needs to be convinced of academic authors' expertise, and this is partly the job of a stronger authorial voice where imprecision is not an issue.

Journal editors can also consider authors' use of hedging to set specific criteria for 'assessing' the quality of the submissions they receive. Assessment criteria can give journals a more objective standard for accepting or rejecting submissions. All in all, hedging is an important part of academic writing, and professionals need to know and use them in their RAs, especially in those sections that are not that precise.

Authors' Statement

This study was supervised by Vahid Ghahraman, who also wrote the first draft of the current paper. Monica Karlsson read, brushed up, and vetted the manuscript. Ali Kazemi is responsible for section 1, 2 and 3. Samira Saeedi is responsible for sections 4, 5 and 6. Ali Elhami controlled and corrected the reference list.

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